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Developing a measurement tool for content engagement across the customer journey: A pilot study

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Abstract

The rise of digital training platforms in Indonesia necessitates the development of robust measurement tools to assess participant engagement effectively. PT Global Edukasi Talenta Incubator (GeTI) implements a Digital Communication Management (DCM) strategy using WhatsApp Business as the main content distribution channel. This study aims to develop a measurement tool to evaluate how different types of content educational, product-related, and cause-related affect content engagement across the customer journey stages: pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase. The research adopts the antecedents and consequences of trust model adapted from Salonen et al. (2024), integrating moderating variables such as brand familiarity and social media usage. A pilot test with 30 respondents was conducted to assess content validity, face validity, and reliability using SPSS. Results showed that all 35 questionnaire items across 7 constructs met the validity (CITC > 0.3) and reliability (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7) thresholds. The proposed measurement tool is therefore appropriate for further use in full-scale studies on digital engagement in educational settings.

Keywords: Content Engagement; Digital Communication; Customer Journey; Social Media; Pilot Test; Educational Content

1. Introduction

PT Global Edukasi Talenta Incubator (GeTI) has implemented a Digital Communication Management (DCM) strategy using a multi-platform approach, with WhatsApp Business as the primary medium for distributing content to trainees. The content shared includes technical information such as training schedules, voucher redemption instructions, facial verification guidance, and task reminders. This strategy is aimed at ensuring that participants receive timely information to complete the full training series optimally (PT Global Edukasi Talenta Incubator, 2024).

Despite adopting a digital approach, GeTI faces several challenges in ensuring the effectiveness of both content and delivery platforms. From a business performance perspective, indicators such as a low delivery rate (12.74% in September 2024) and a high pending rate (61.70%–72.70% from June to August 2024) indicate technical constraints that hinder participant engagement. A sharp decline in conversation volume during non-campaign periods illustrates the reliance on well-planned communication strategies. Additionally, low customer service efficiency only five conversations were resolved during the May to September 2024 period emphasizes the need for systematic improvements (PT Global Edukasi Talenta Incubator, 2024).

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2. Literature review

Shahbaznezhad et al. (2021) categorize engaging content into three main types: rational, transactional, and interactional. Rational content delivers useful and helpful information; transactional content provides direct incentives for purchases, such as product announcements, discounts, or contests; while interactional content aims to build emotional experiences and relationships to satisfy users' desires for social integration.

This study follows the framework of Salonen et al. (2024), which explicitly segments the customer journey into pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase stages. Adopting a B2C adaptation of the B2B model, this research proposes that customers engage with educational, product-related, or cause-related content that aligns with their journey stage, thereby increasing content and firm engagement. These relationships are moderated by timing and social media usage. Salonen et al.'s hypotheses on content relevance, engagement pathways, mediating roles, and social media effects inform this study's conceptual framework. Figure 1 shows the proposed the antecedents and consequences model of this research.

Figure 1 The antecedents of consequences model of trust as research framework

This study uses a structured online questionnaire as the main research instrument. It evaluates the following variables

- Independent Variables: Content types (educational, product-related, and cause-related) and brand familiarity, measured based on perceived suitability across customer journey stages.
- Dependent Variable: Content engagement, including likelihood to like, share, act upon, and perceive relevance.
- Moderating Variable: Social media usage (frequency of using WhatsApp to seek content).

This study is similar to Indrawati et al. (2023), who examined how eWOM via TikTok affected consumers purchasing intentions, focusing particularly on how social media platforms function as key channels for distributing digital content. This study also aligns with the research methods of Indrawati and Putri (2018) and Indrawati et al. (2022), who also employed a survey approach to study real digital activities (online buying or technology adoption) without laboratory experiments, therefore compiling data based on real behavior. To ensure the quality of the measurement tool, the study conducted content validity, face validity, readability tests, and a pilot test with 30 respondents. Content validity was ensured by adapting published items; face validity involved expert feedback in marketing and digital media; and readability tested respondents' comprehension.

3. Methodology

To develop a good measurement tool, the validity and reliability test are conducted in this research. Validity tests are consisting of content validity, face validity, readability and pilot test. Indrawati (2015) explains that content validity is the extent to which items are used to measure the research variables logically correspond to what is measured and conducted by adopting and modifying items related with what has been published. Face validity was conducted by expecting some suggestions and recommendations from the experts in the field of marketing. Readability was conducted through the results of respondents understanding toward the questionnaire. Table 1 shows the items of questionnaire.

Table 1 Items on Questionnaire

Variable	Item Code	Statement (English)
Brand Familiarity	BF1	Before viewing GeTI content, how familiar were you with GeTI Incubator?
	BF2	While interacting with GeTI content, how familiar are you with the GeTI Incubator brand?
	BF3	After interacting with GeTI content, how familiar are you with the GeTI Incubator brand?
Content Fit	CF1	How well does the educational content from GeTI Incubator match your current learning needs?
	CF2	How appropriate is the product content from GeTI Incubator for your training or product-related needs?
	CF3	How well does the cause-related content from GeTI Incubator align with the social context you are facing?
	CF4	To what extent does your current situation affect the relevance of the content provided by GeTI Incubator?
Educational Content	EC1	How informative is the educational content from GeTI Incubator in helping you understand the services offered?
	EC2	How clearly does the educational content from GeTI Incubator explain the material presented?
	EC3	How much does the educational content from GeTI Incubator motivate you to explore the topic more deeply?
	EC4	How well does the educational content from GeTI Incubator help you understand the material more effectively?
Product Content	PC1	How informative is the product content from GeTI Incubator in helping you understand the offering before making a decision?
	PC2	How clearly does the product content from GeTI Incubator explain the benefits of the offered product?
	PC3	How persuasive is the product content from GeTI Incubator in influencing your purchase intention?
	PC4	How well does the product content from GeTI Incubator match your current personal interests?
Cause-Related Content	CC1	To what extent does the cause-related content from GeTI Incubator reflect concern for social issues?
	CC2	How influential is the cause-related content from GeTI Incubator in raising your awareness about the addressed social issues?
	CC3	How interested are you in participating in social movements after viewing GeTI Incubator's cause-related content?
	CC4	How well does the cause-related content from GeTI Incubator align with your personal values?
Social Media Usage	SM1	How often do you receive information about educational content from GeTI Incubator through WhatsApp?
	SM2	How often do you receive information about product content from GeTI Incubator through WhatsApp?

	SM3	How often do you receive information about cause-related content from GeTI Incubator through WhatsApp?
Content Engagement	CE1	How likely are you to "like" content from GeTI Incubator?
	CE2	How likely are you to share content from GeTI Incubator with your friends?
	CE3	How likely are you to search for more information after viewing content from GeTI Incubator?
	CE4	How relevant is GeTI Incubator's content to your learning needs?
	CE5	How often do you recall content from GeTI Incubator a few days after seeing it?
	CE6	How well does GeTI Incubator's content match your personal interests?

4. Results and discussion

The pilot test was conducted on 30 respondents through Google Forms online questionnaire. All respondents are representatives of those having domiciled in Indonesia. This study employs a quantitative approach to empirically test the impact of various content types, including educational, product-related, and cause-related content, on content engagement among trainee participants at PT Global Edukasi Talenta Incubator (GeTI). The data collected was calculated by using SPSS software. Refers to Freidenberg and Kaplan in Indrawati (2015:149), the items are considered to be valid if the "Corrected Item - Total Correlation" (CITC) is greater than 0.3. All of the items on seven constructs in this research are considered to be valid. As well as the reliability test is where the Cronbach-Alpha (CA) score greater than 0.7. All seven constructs in this research satisfy the reliability test. The results of the pilot test present in the following Table 2.

Table 2 Pilot Test Result

Variable	Item Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha (CA)
Educational Content	EC1	789	814
	EC2	906	
	EC3	673	
	EC4	425	
Product Content	PC1	782	806
	PC2	848	
	PC3	370	
	PC4	540	
Cause-Related Content	CC1	884	876
	CC2	549	
	CC3	689	
	CC4	792	
Social Media Usage	SM1	669	895
	SM2	936	
	SM3	823	
Content Fit	CF1	879	817
	CF2	306	
	CF3	621	
	CF4	758	

Brand Familiarity	BF1	468	768
	BF2	874	
	BF3	693	
Content Engagement	CE1	274	852
	CE2	716	
	CE3	829	
	CE4	845	
	CE5	614	
	CE6	778	

5. Conclusion

This pilot study successfully developed and tested a measurement tool to evaluate the impact of educational, product-related, and cause-related content on content engagement across different stages of the customer journey at PT Global Edukasi Talenta Incubator (GeTI). The instrument was designed based on the modified antecedents and consequences of the trust model by Salonen et al. (2024) and further enriched with contextual relevance to GeTI's digital communication strategy via WhatsApp Business. Using validity and reliability tests on 35 items across 7 constructs with 30 respondents, the results showed that all indicators met the minimum standards of Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC > 0.3) and Cronbach's Alpha (CA > 0.7). These findings confirm that the developed measurement tool is both valid and reliable for evaluating content engagement in digital learning environments. This tool is now ready for application in full-scale research to analyze behavioral patterns and improve content strategies tailored to customer journey stages within digital education platforms.

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